

Centering Community in Language Preservation Building Speech Transcription for Khroskyabs

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ABSTRACT

Automatic Speech Recognition can be a valuable tool for work in preserving Endangered Languages. The endangered language, Khroskyabs, is spoken by members of a village on the Tibetan Plateau who have been working with a linguist from their community on language preservation efforts. Machine learning and artificial intelligence tools can assist in language preservation. When preservation work is done by those outside the community, they must use technology with great care to maintain the respect that the community and language deserve. In this project, we demonstrate an example of how to prioritize an ethical framework to allow all linguists to accomplish language preservation goals.

KEYWORDS: Khroskyabs; Endangered Languages; Speech Technology; Ethics

INTRODUCTION

Khroskyabs /tʂʰo scæv/ is a Tibeto-Burman language of the northwestern Sichuan province in the People's Republic of China. The 6,000 to 10,000 worldwide speakers of Khroskyabs identify as ethnically Tibetan. In this area, the speakers of Khroskyabs are often farmers living in the valleys (Lawa, 2021).

Khroskyabs is a highly agglutinative language with long consonant clusters. The language builds words by combining morphemes (small pieces) that each carry a specific meaning. A single word in an agglutinative language can translate into an entire sentence in English. Khroskyabs borrows significantly from both the prestige language of the community, Amdo Tibetan, and the language of schooling, Sichuan Mandarin (Taylor-Adams & Lhawa, 2021). Khroskyabs is an oral language and lacks an orthography, thus it has no writing system used by speakers to visually represent their language.

These characteristics make Khroskyabs vulnerable to linguistic erosion, underscoring the importance of developing tools to aid in its preservation and revitalization.

BACKGROUND

Community members have been leading efforts to preserve Khroskyabs. Co-author Yulha Lhawa has been making audio recordings for over 15 years during her career as a linguist.

A popular preservation method is transcription of audio recordings. Even for a linguist familiar with Khroskyabs, it can take up to an hour to transcribe one minute of recorded audio. To date, approximately three hours of audio have been transcribed by linguists using the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). This transcription process is often referred to as the “transcription bottleneck” because it is a labor-intensive and time-consuming process. ASR tools must be adapted carefully, or they risk misunderstanding or misrepresenting the language.

MOTIVATION

Using machine learning and AI to document the Khroskyabs language is a new and relatively unexplored area. There is no published material on how to manage the process for Khroskyabs. In this project, we demonstrate how implementing ethical AI principles at the conception stage of an Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) project can provide a structure to continue to guide the team during the Construction, Use, and Evaluation phases of the project.

We followed the Ethical Principles for Language Resources and Language Technology (Kamocki & Witt, 2022) taxonomy prioritizing “Privacy, Property, Equality, Transparency and Freedom.” Establishing clear guidelines and obtaining team agreements allowed us to produce quality work that aligned with our personal and academic values while respecting the wishes and contributions from the community.

METHODS

We chose to support the community by working to develop an ASR System. An ASR system uses artificial intelligence or machine learning to process human speech into readable text. An efficient ASR system can significantly speed up the transcription process, leaving more time for linguists to spend with the community. We used Praat (Boersma & Weenink, n.d.) for human text alignment, Montreal Forced Aligner (McAuliffe et al., 2017) for machine learning text alignment, and Elpis (Foley et al., 2018) for automatic transcription.

CENTERING COMMUNITY

With each phase of the process, we considered and addressed how project goals could be accomplished in alignment with this ethical framework. Rather than evaluating the impacts of our tool after development, we adapted the proposed questions from Kamocki & Witt (2022) for use in our project:

Conception Phase

- Under whose responsibility is the tool or resource developed? What is the intended purpose of the tool? What are the potential uses and foreseeable misuses? What are the intended user groups? What is the potential impact on the users?

Construction Phase

- Are the data subject to intellectual property rights? Is the individual allowed to opt-out?

Use Phase

- Is the tool suitable for the envisaged use? What are our terms of use?

Evaluation Phase

- Who is responsible for this tool? Is the tool being used for its initial purpose or has the use changed? Are the actual users the same as the intended users?

We also evaluated each of the five ethical principles detailed by Kamocki & Witt (2022) to determine how they applied to our work:

Privacy: All software used in our workflow was operated locally by team members or on a departmental server, allowing us to retain full data security and maintain data privacy.

We used audio files recorded over the past 15 years by the co-author in her village. During the alignment process, non-Khroskyabs speakers listened to the audio files to align the sounds with the transcriptions. Their lack of understanding of the language was an informal firewall preventing them from understanding anything that was heard, thus preventing the transmission of personal information. Verbal consent from all participants was obtained before recording for linguistic analysis and language tool development.

To ensure privacy and protect the anonymity of the speakers, we have removed all speaker IDs during the transcription process. We had high background noise files that were in various formats and needed to be converted to WAV files for alignment. We chose a company based in Europe and bound by the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Property: The audio data is on loan to the team and remains the property of the original speakers.

Equality: We strive to build a tool that values all speakers' contributions fairly and without negative impact. Including the community as equal partners could allow customizations such as teaching the tool new sounds or forms.

Transparency: Our team informs villagers about the progress of preservation work, thereby fostering a direct and meaningful connection with the community and working with them as equal partners. All computer-generated outputs are distinguished from human-made analyses, and we transparently identify the data source.

Freedom: The speakers freely contributed to this project and are free to withdraw their consent at any time. If consent is withdrawn, the model will be rebuilt without their data.

RESULTS AND EVALUATION

We were able to align 135 minutes of audio by hand and 66 minutes of audio using the MFA, resulting in 201 minutes of audio aligned with the transcription. Our model's word error rate of around 70% is comparable to the expected word error rate for speech recognition models with similar amounts of training data (Slam et. al, 2023). The most significant challenge is the lack of transcribed audio data. Few people in the world are working on this language and we have access to most of the audio data that has been collected. With more high-quality transcribed data, the model would be improved and will provide an effective and useful tool for the preservation and revitalization of Khroskyabs.

CONCLUSION

We were able to achieve creditable ASR results in this low-data setting, while adhering to the ethical goals of Privacy, Property, Equality, Transparency, and Freedom in supporting language preservation efforts for Khroskyabs. We invite other researchers to consider this approach.

GENERATIVE AI USE

We confirm that we did not use generative AI tools/services to author this submission.

AUTHOR ATTRIBUTION

JW: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, methodology, software, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing; YL: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation, writing – original draft; JC: conceptualization, data curation, methodology, writing – original draft; CZ: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, methodology, software, writing – original draft.

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